

Experimental Assessment Multiband Lossless ROADM Architecture for Optical Metro Access Network

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Abstract We experimentally assess an SOA-based multiband lossless multi-degree reconfigurable optical add/drop multiplexer (MB-ROADM) for metropolitan networks. Results show -33.8dB cross-talk, lossless and error-free transmission with average power penalties of 1.2dB and 1.8dB at 10^{-9} for C-band channels at 53Gbps and for O-band at 25Gbps, respectively.

Introduction

The growth in demand for data transmission is relentless boosted by applications such as VR/AR metaverse, Digital Twins, volumetric video transmission, and more. As a result, in the medium and long term, each access aggregation node will need to handle traffic of 2 Tbps and 8 Tbps and the traffic for Metro-hub within the Metro Core Network is projected to be 29.3 Tbps and 114.8 Tbps [1], respectively. Carrying such large traffic loads can be done by the use of multiband technology beyond the C-band, as it significantly increases fiber capacity without the need for laying new fibers. Additionally, multiband systems offer the capability to allocate different bands for various services or user groups, thereby enhancing the network's flexibility. This flexibility is particularly advantageous for dynamically adjusting resources in response to changing application, capacity and link reach demands facilitated by software-defined networking. Optical metro and access networks already adopt metro hubs and multi-horseshoe network topology as shown in Fig.1. O-band transmission can be exploited in short link horseshoe metro-access networks leveraging C-band transmission for long link between hubs in the metro-core network [2]. In order to transparently and flexibly operate the MBT metro network in a cost-efficient way preserving both the ability to share edges among different connections and provide intra-node connectivity to flexibly route carriers across the network [3], the metro hub node should be equipped with a multiband (O+C band) multi-degree ROADM architecture.

Despite the commercial availability of ROADM in C-band [4-7], there is no multi-degree ROADM in O-band to date. Several Wavelength Selective Switches (WSS), the main building block to implement a ROADM, operating in O-band have been demonstrated[8]. Semiconductor Optical Amplifiers(SOA)-based WSS has the advantages

Fig. 1: Multiple Horseshoe Metro Access Network Topology

of optical amplification (lossless operation and power equalization), high on/off ratio, fast switching speed, and operate across different wavelength bands[2]. Moreover, SOA based WSS can be seamlessly integrated into a photonic circuit for large volume and low cost manufacturing [7,9].

In this paper, we propose and experimentally demonstrate a lossless multi-degree multiband (C+O) ROADM architecture for optical metro networks. Experimental results of the ROADM with C-band and O-band channels at 53Gbps and 25Gbps, respectively, confirm lossless operation, extinct ratio > 34 dB in the C band and >60dB in the O band, dynamic reconfiguration of the channels, and error free operation with average power penalty at BER of 10^{-9} of 1.2dB for C-band and 1.8 dB for O-band, respectively.

Architecture of Multiband 4-Port ROADM

The 4-port Multiband ROADM architecture, depicted in Fig. 2, is designed to accommodate multi-band and multiple port network configurations. The architecture comprises three inputs originating from the Metro (as an example, considering Fig. 1, the inputs from Hub4, Access Network1, and Access Network 2), and the fourth input is the add port. The optical power of each input ports is split using a 1X4 splitter to broadcast the MB channels to the corresponding multiband wavelength blockers (MB-WB) at the output ports (including the drop port). At each output port, four

MB-WBs are employed to either block or bypass the traffic from the 3 input ports and the add port. The traffic passed by the MB-WBs is then combined using a 4X1 combiner to the output port. The Drop port is a 1X3 coupler and 3 MB-WBs for dropping traffic from three input ports.

The design of the MB-WB is shown in Fig. 3(b) and consists of a band demultiplexer and multiplexer used to separate and combine the input MB signals. For each band, the WB incorporates a WDM demultiplexer, an array of SOAs operating as gates and amplifiers for dynamic blocking/passing of each WDM channel, and a WDM multiplexer. Notably, each SOA operates with a single channel to mitigate nonlinearities that could degrade signal quality. The gain of the SOA compensates for ROADM and can also be used with an external power monitoring system as channel equalizer.

Experimental setup and results

The experimental setup for evaluating the multiport ROADM is depicted in Fig. 3(a). In the C-band, we utilized six DWDM channels at $\lambda_1=1557.36\text{nm}$, $\lambda_2=1555.75\text{nm}$, $\lambda_3=1554.13\text{nm}$, $\lambda_4=1552.52\text{nm}$, $\lambda_5=1550.92\text{nm}$, and $\lambda_6=1549.32\text{nm}$ at 53 Gbps OOK-NRZ data streams with a pseudorandom bit sequence (PRBS) length of $2^{13}-1$. For the O-band, commercial pluggable O-band LAN WDM (LWDM) transceivers were employed, each supporting four 25Gbps OOK-NRZ data streams with $2^{13}-1$ PRBS. The O-band channels were operated at wavelengths of $\lambda_7=1294.5\text{nm}$, $\lambda_8=1299.5\text{nm}$, $\lambda_9=1304.5\text{nm}$, and $\lambda_{10}=1309.5\text{nm}$.

Figure 4 displays the spectral results of different configurations of the ROADM. In Figure 4(a), the ROADM is configured such that all wavelengths from Input 1 pass through Output 1, while all other input ports are blocked. For the C-band, the OSNR of the input six wavelengths are 67.5 dB, 66 dB, 67 dB, 66 dB, 67 dB, and 68 dB. After

Fig. 2: Architecture of the 4-Degree Multiband ROADM.

passing through the ROADM, the OSNR of each wavelength becomes 42 dB, 37 dB, 38 dB, 39 dB, 38 dB, and 41 dB. Similarly, for the O-band, the OSNR of the four wavelengths is 61.47 dB, 61.5 dB, 61.5 dB, and 59.8 dB in B2B. After traversing the ROADM, the OSNR of each wavelength becomes 43 dB, 44 dB, 44 dB, and 40 dB.

The ROADM total loss is 18.5dB (12dB from the two 1x4 couplers, 1.5dB from two band demux/mux, 5dB from the two WDM demux/mux). The SOAs operate ~ 225 mA in C-band to provide ~ 18.5 dB gain with <0.6 dB PDG, and O-band SOAs provide ~ 18.5 dB gain and <0.2 dB PDG at 250 mA. The SOAs compensate the ROADM losses as can be observed by the zoom-in WDM spectra in Fig 4(a) for both bands.

In a second example, we assess the add and drop operation with full input traffic from all input ports. As a possible routing example, it is assumed that based on instructions from the control plane data at λ_1 and λ_7 from input 3 and input 1 will be dropped and new traffic will be added at same wavelength to output 1. Data at λ_2 , λ_3 , and λ_4 from input 3, 2, 1 will bypass to output 1. Data at λ_6 and

Fig. 3: a) Schematic of the experiment setup; b) Architecture of the Multiband (C- and O-band) Wavelength Blocker.

Fig. 4: a) Spectra of C-band and O-band channels from Input 1 to Output 1, and other input ports blocked. The subplot is the zoom-in of each channel b) Spectra of WDM channels from all inputs switched to different Output ports.

Fig. 5: a) Bit Error Rate of C Band with 53Gbps NRZ b) Bit Error Rate of O Band with 25Gbps NRZ

λ_8 from input 2 and 1 will bypass to output 2, and λ_5 , λ_9 , and λ_{10} from input 1,2,3 will bypass to output 3. All the other channels will be blocked. Figure 4(b) reports the outputs and drop port spectra according to the desired routing. From the drop port we can observe an extinction ratios for the O-band larger than 60dB, while for the C-band larger than 34 dB. This effectively isolates the output channels in the ROADM from the input signal thus enabling wavelength reuse in the metro network. The crosstalk in both C- and O-band of output 1,2,3 is below -60 dB and -34 dB (worst case). Figure 5 reports the results of the bit error rate test conducted for both the C-band (Fig.5(a)) and O-band(Fig.5(b)) channels. At output 1, the power penalties for wavelengths λ_2 , λ_3 , and λ_4 at a bit error rate of $10e-9$ level are 1.5 dB, 1.6 dB, and 1 dB, respectively. For output 2, the power penalties for wavelengths λ_2 in the C-band and λ_8 in the O-band are 1.2 dB and 2.8 dB, respectively. At output 3, the power penalties for wavelengths λ_3 , λ_9 , and λ_{10} are 0.75 dB, 1.55 dB, and 1.75 dB, respectively. The power penalties for the add traffic at wavelengths λ_1 and λ_7 are 1 dB and 1.8 dB,

respectively, while for the drop traffic, they are 1.6 dB and 2.1 dB, respectively. Note that MB-WB is used for the add port to already assess future directionless and bidirectional implementation.

Conclusions

We have proposed and demonstrated a multi-band (C+O band) lossless multiport ROADM exploiting SOA-based multiband WBs. Experimental results validated the dynamic switching, dropping, and adding operation of the MB-ROADM with high extinction ratios and low crosstalk. The amplification provided by the SOA compensates the ROADM insertion losses and in principle using SOA with higher gain (25 dB has been demonstrated in [10]), the ROADM architecture can extend to more ports. The output average OSNR of 42dB and 38dB in the C- and O-band was measured. BER measurements for all channels at 53Gbps NRZ (C-band) and 25Gbps NRZ (O-band) confirmed error-free operation with average power penalties of 1.2dB and 1.8 dB in the C-band and O-band, respectively.

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